

Insight into Mo₂C Nanoplates Growth by Means of Scanning Electrochemical Cell Microscopy for High-Resolution Electrocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Activity Mapping

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Molybdenum carbides have emerged as promising catalysts for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER). While numerous studies have investigated synthesis methods, structural properties, and their application, the understanding of their local electrochemical behavior and the correlation between particle size and activity remains elusive. This study addresses this gap by carrying out a comprehensive investigation of the HER activity of well-defined morphologies and sizes of α -Mo₂C nanoplates, grown via chemical vapor deposition. Scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM) is employed for high-resolution HER mapping on flakes with dimensions ranging from 1 μm to 40 μm in lateral size, using SECCM capillaries with ≈ 130 nm tip diameter. Our findings reveal a significant variability in the HER activity at the subparticle level, suggesting that the heterogeneous activity observed in pristine flakes larger than 10 μm is due to an addition of effects caused by the long-term growth, such as step-edge formation, Mo₂C oxidation, and the presence of residual graphene. This study underscores the importance of local characterization of individual Mo₂C nanoplates, shedding light on the impact of size-dependence on the HER activity.

1. Introduction

Transition metal carbides (TMCs) are a group of interstitial compounds formed between group IV–VI transition metals and carbon. TMCs exhibit a combination of physical properties typically found in metals and ceramics, such as high electrical conductivity, melting point, and hardness.^[1] Molybdenum carbides (Mo₂C) have garnered significant attention due to their remarkable physicochemical properties,^[2] making them suitable for various applications, including energy storage,^[3] sensing,^[4] and catalysis.^[5–14]

Mo₂C is a promising electrocatalyst for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) due to its high catalytic activity and stability in both acidic and alkaline environments.^[5,6,8,15] Various studies have shown that Mo₂C nanomaterials, especially those with engineered surfaces and structures,

exhibit enhanced HER performance. For example, Bang et al. demonstrated that a structure with multiple step-edges of

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α -Mo₂C nanosheets achieved efficient HER activity across a wide pH range.^[9] In addition to HER, Mo₂C is also reported as a catalyst for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR).^[10–12] Zhang et al. pointed to the potential of quasi-paired Pt atomic sites on Mo₂C for running ORR with high selectivity for the four-electron transfer reaction to water,^[10] with valuable performance for fuel cell applications. Furthermore, Mo₂C has also been explored for electrochemical CO₂ reduction reaction.^[13,14] Likith also discussed the increased thermodynamic stability of orthorhombic Mo₂C due to the formation of molybdenum oxycarbides during the CO₂ reduction reaction.^[14] These studies have shed light on the exploration of Mo₂C as a promising catalyst for energy conversion reactions.

Structurally, the stability and performance of Mo₂C can be enhanced through precise control of the material size and phase composition.^[16–18] However, there is a lack of a deeper understanding of the relationship between material size and electrochemical activity. Generally, thinner and larger 2D Mo₂C nanoplates exhibit a higher surface area-to-volume ratio, leading to a higher number of active sites on the basal plane. Recent efforts have focused on implementing a bottom-up or top-down approach to synthesize 2D Mo₂C. The former are known as nonlayered ultrathin TMCs (UThTMCs) and the latter are known as layered MXenes. In this context, Wu et al. implemented a bottom-up salt-assisted, methane carburization route to synthesize ultrathin Mo₂C.^[7] Microcell devices probed selected regions of the Mo₂C flakes and a high HER performance was measured on the edge and on thin flakes (0.36 nm).^[7] Xu et al. developed a bottom-up, liquid-metal-assisted chemical vapor deposition (LMCVD) process to synthesize faceted, highly crystalline, UThTMC nanoplates with a thickness down to a few nanometers (3.4 nm) and tens of micrometers lateral area.^[2] Geng et al. grew ultrathin Mo₂C, on copper-molybdenum foils using LMCVD, with good HER performance.^[19]

While the HER performance of 2D Mo₂C has been previously studied, the lateral size-activity relationship has not been considered since conventional electrochemical measurements typically involve measuring a relatively large sample area, where a wide size distribution of materials is considered. Therefore, we employed scanning electrochemical cell microscopy (SECCM) to locally characterize individually the electrochemical activity of diverse sizes of Mo₂C. SECCM has emerged as a pivotal technique for investigating local electrochemical properties at the nanoscale^[20–23] mainly applied for acquiring electrocatalytic activity mapping of nanoparticles^[23–25] and 2D materials^[26–32] such as graphene^[26] and transition metal dichalcogenides.^[33–35] SECCM can reveal differences in activity at the nanoscale and with subparticle measurements, being capable of resolving the electrochemical behavior within individual sections inside a single nanoparticle.^[25,36] This technique enables the correlation of physical and chemical properties with catalytic performance, which is essential for optimizing catalysts at the nanoscale. Advanced microscopy techniques such as SECCM are crucial for gaining deeper insights into nanoscale electrochemical processes, guiding the optimization of synthesis methods for enhanced catalytic performance.

Recently, SECCM was applied to explore the electrochemical behavior of a MXene.^[37] This study employed cyclic voltammetry (CV) and electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) to

investigate the properties of a Ti₃C₂T_x MXene. The findings indicated that the pseudocapacitive behavior of Ti₃C₂T_x is primarily attributed to its unique surface chemistry and structure, which facilitate fast and reversible redox reactions. The results demonstrated a significant increase in capacitance with higher scan rates, highlighting the dominance of surface-controlled processes. Additionally, the EIS data revealed low charge transfer resistance and high capacitance, further confirming the efficient pseudocapacitive performance of Ti₃C₂T_x. To the best of our knowledge, no studies have used SECCM to understand the local electrochemical properties of Mo₂C UThTMC nanoplates of different sizes.

Therefore, SECCM was employed systematically to provide nanoscale mappings of the HER activity of Mo₂C UThTMC nanoplates in acidic media. A comprehensive study of the HER activity of single hexagonal Mo₂C nanoplates with sizes ranging from 2 to 50 μ m in lateral size was performed using nanoscale SECCM probes with \approx 130 nm tip diameter. Our findings reveal significant variability in HER activity at the subparticle level, with nanoplates smaller than 10 μ m exhibiting higher HER activity than larger nanoplates (>10 μ m). We attributed this behavior to a convolution of effects: size-dependent formation of step-edges and native Mo oxide during the CVD growth, and the presence of residual graphene. The correlation between the electrochemical activity of Mo₂C with the material size was supported by atomic force microscopy (AFM), transmission electron microscopy (TEM), energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX), Raman spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS).

2. Results and Discussion

The size dependence of the electrochemical activity of Mo₂C nanoplates at the subparticle level was systematically investigated by employing a high-resolution SECCM to map the local electrochemical activity towards HER. Mo₂C nanoplates were grown via a controllable atmospheric pressure liquid metal chemical vapor deposition process,^[2] as detailed in the supporting information. As depicted in Figure S1, Supporting Information, Mo atoms diffuse through the liquid copper foil and react with methane on the Cu surface. The copper foil thickness, methane-hydrogen concentration, and growth duration serve as the basis to control the growth of specific lateral sizes, nucleation density, and thickness of the Mo₂C nanoplates.^[38]

Optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM), were employed to evaluate the effect of copper thickness, methane concentration and growth time, and tune the synthesis parameters to achieve the desired nanoplates' lateral size and thickness. Optical microscopy and SEM imaging provided a distribution of lateral lengths for the nanoplates, as illustrated in **Figure 1** and S2, Supporting Information. The predominant morphology of Mo₂C appears to be hexagonal prisms with a lateral side length varying from 2 μ m to 50 μ m. Two samples were selected for the electrochemical study and described in the supporting information. Summarizing, Sample I was prepared with parameters to induce flakes with small size, resulting in Mo₂C nanoplates with lateral size distribution of $5.3 \pm 2.4 \mu$ m (Figure 1A,B). While Sample II was grown by maintaining

Figure 1. Analysis performed on A,B) Sample I and C,D) Sample II. A,C) Morphology is seen from optical microscopy and B,D) distribution of Mo₂C lateral size.

parameters to achieve large lateral-sized flakes. Sample II Mo₂C flakes presented a size distribution of $14.0 \pm 12.8 \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 1C,D). Note that Sample II growth protocol provided a broad size distribution with the presence of small (lateral sizes $<10 \mu\text{m}$) and large flakes ($>10 \mu\text{m}$). Interestingly, the formation of step-edges in Sample II was observed frequently, which was probably provoked due to an excess of molybdenum on the surface due to the long growth time.^[39]

The thickness of the two samples of Mo₂C nanoplates was determined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) on nanoplates transferred to thermally oxidized silicon (SiO₂/Si) substrates, utilizing the wet chemical transfer method (as outlined in the Supporting Information). The nanoplate thickness ranged from 40 nm to 150 nm, demonstrating the formation of ultrathin nanoplates (Figure S3, Supporting Information), depending on the processing conditions. AFM data revealed a correlation between the lateral size and the thickness of the nanoplates, where the thickness was inversely proportional to the nanoplate's size. Specifically, the Mo₂C flakes on Sample II, with lateral size $>10 \mu\text{m}$, were observed to be thinner than the nanoplates in Sample I, with lateral size $<10 \mu\text{m}$. This could be related to the vertical and lateral growth modes studied by Buke et al. with varying the copper thicknesses and growth time.^[38] We note, however, that since the copper foils are stacked on to the molybdenum foil, there is a challenge in maintaining a uniform flux of molybdenum across the entire substrate which could lead to a distribution of nanoplate thicknesses.

2.1. Correlative Mapping of Topographic and Electrochemical Properties of the Sample I and Sample II Flakes

The electrochemical activity SECCM mapping was performed by recording voltammograms to follow the local HER. The SECCM tip was filled with $10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$, and the map was performed on flakes of the Sample I (Figure 2) and Sample II (Figure 3). The HER was selected as an inner-sphere electron transfer reaction, since it is highly dependent on the physicochemical properties of the catalyst surface, making it a valuable probe for studying structure-activity relationships.

High-resolution HER current maps of single Mo₂C flakes were obtained using nanoscale SECCM probes with $\approx 130 \text{ nm}$ tip diameter, as seen in Figure S4, Supporting Information, according to the methodology detailed in the supporting information. AFM topography image performed after the SECCM measurements reveals that the SECCM droplet size had an effective spot diameter of $214 \pm 1 \text{ nm}$ (Figure S5, Supporting Information), confirming that the SECCM resolution covered subparticle resolution.

SECCM can also provide a topographical image of the sample during the acquisition of electrochemical activity maps. This feature allowed us to correlate topographical SECCM, morphological (SEM), topographical AFM data, and electrochemical (SECCM) information, respectively, as shown in Figure 2A–D. As depicted in Figure 2A–C by morphological and topographical imaging, two out of the three Mo₂C nanoplates of Sample I

Figure 2. Morphological and local electrochemical characterization of Mo₂C nanoplates grown on sample I. A) SECCM topographic mapping constructed from the z-piezo extension. B) SEM image using secondary electrons and electron acceleration voltage of 5 kV. C) AFM topography image acquired in the noncontact mode. D) SECCM mapping of HER current at -0.6 V versus RHE. E) Tafel slope mapping calculated between -0.40 and -0.55 V vs RHE. F) AFM height profile extracted from lines 1 and 2 in (C). Representative LSV curves for G) flake 1, H) flake 2, and I) flake 3 are numbered in (D). The (x, y) coordinates from where the LSV curves were extracted are shown in the legend. LSV curves were obtained in $10 \text{ mmol L}^{-1} \text{ HClO}_4$ with scan rate of 2 V s^{-1} . SECCM image was acquired with a hopping distance of 500 nm and SECCM tip of 130 nm diameter.

Figure 3. SECCM mappings for Mo₂C nanoplates in Sample II showing A) the HER current at -0.6 V versus RHE and C) the Tafel slopes calculated between -0.4 and -0.55 V versus RHE acquired with a hopping distance of $1 \mu\text{m}$. B) Current and D) Tafel slope histograms were extracted for the big flake (flake 4, orange bars) and small flake (flake 5, blue bars), respectively. The inset in (A) shows the optical microscopy image of the measured flakes. HR-TEM of α -Mo₂C nanoplates at E, F) the basal plane and G, H) the cross-section plane.

displayed a hexagonal shape, while one appeared rectangular. These flakes were also visualized in the central bottom part of Figure 1A. Figure 2D,E demonstrates the capability of SECCM to locally measuring the HER electrochemical activity covering nanoplates and subparticle information, while differentiating the activity of the basal plane and the edges.

Regardless of the nanoplate geometry, all three Mo₂C flakes measured in Sample I have lateral sizes below 10 μm and exhibited smooth basal planes with low surface roughness without step-edges. This observation was confirmed by SEM and AFM analyses (Figure 2B,C, respectively), revealing flat surfaces with edges “buried” in the Cu substrate. The AFM height profile (Figure 2F) illustrates that the edges of both hexagonal nanoplates (depicted by the red line) are notably more prominent than the basal plane, evident from the increased height at the edges, also visualized in the SECCM topographical mapping (Figure 2A). Additionally, the hexagonal Mo₂C nanoplates’ basal plane surface lies below the Cu surface because the growth involves Mo diffusion through Cu. In contrast, the behavior of the rectangular nanoplate is distinct, growing “out” of the copper surface, as shown by the black line in Figure 2F. AFM and SEM revealed particulate features at the nanoplate edges attributed to copper oxide particles. Raman spectroscopy (Figure S6, Supporting Information) shows the presence of particles on the edges of Mo₂C flakes which match the Raman signature of copper oxide. STEM-EDS mapping of transferred and isolated flakes in Figure S7, Supporting Information, shows copper oxide particles present on the basal plane which we attribute to the incompletely etched copper substrate. The absence of copper oxide particles on the edges of the Mo₂C flakes is consistent with the interpretation that these particles originate from the oxidized copper substrate and are not intrinsic features of the Mo₂C flakes. The AFM and SEM images align with the topographical SECCM image in Figure 2A.

The HER activity of Mo₂C nanoplates in Sample I (Figure 2D), appeared relatively uniform, suggesting homogeneity across the basal plane. The current range for all three nanoplates was about –800 pA at –0.6 V vs RHE, indicating that differences in flake morphology do not significantly influence electrochemical activity. The short growth time used in Sample I also resulted also in a homogeneous copper surface, observed in the activity SECCM mapping (yellow color—current range < –50 pA), indicating uniform but relatively poor HER activity, accentuating the contrast compared to the active small Mo₂C nanoplates.

Representative linear sweep voltammetry curves (LSVs) of each flake were selected and plotted in Figure 2G–I, to delve deeper into the local electrochemical behavior. Figure 2G–I illustrates findings for the rectangular-shaped Mo₂C nanoplate (flake 1), the central hexagonal Mo₂C nanoplate (flake 2), and the right hexagonal Mo₂C nanoplate (flake 3), respectively. For all three flakes, a consistent pattern emerged: Both the edge and basal plane of the flakes demonstrated significantly enhanced performance, characterized by elevated currents and improved HER activity when compared with the Cu surface. As previously discussed, at the nanoplates’ edges, there is an interface between the Mo₂C nanoplates and the Cu substrate that exhibits a distinct topographical profile. The LSV curves extracted from the edges exhibit lower HER activity (Figure 2G–I), probably resulting from SECCM tip landing on the heterogeneity. This

reduced activity is primarily attributed to the growth mechanism, where Mo diffuses through the Cu foil during synthesis.

It is important to note that the copper oxide particles in the nanoplates’ edge do not dominate the HER activity (Figure 2D). The rectangular Mo₂C flake presented in Figure 2 offers additional evidence that residual copper does not block the catalytically active sites at the edges. In this case, the flake clearly grows out of the Cu substrate, with more exposed edges, as confirmed by the corresponding AFM image in Figure 2B,C, which shows increased flake height and minimal particle coverage at the periphery. Notably, the electrochemical activity of this rectangular flake is comparable to that of neighboring hexagonal flakes, as shown in the SECCM current and Tafel slope maps (Figure 2D,E), suggesting that the edge activity is not significantly impeded by copper oxide clusters.

Additionally, Tafel analysis conducted between –400 and –550 mV versus RHE (Figure 2E) revealed a Tafel slope close to 70 mV dec^{–1} for all three analyzed flakes, thus confirming uniformity irrespective of geometry. Notably, the difference between some spots at the edge became more apparent in the Tafel plot, displaying higher and random Tafel slope values in Figure 2E. All Tafel plots and their respective regions can be found in Figure S8, Supporting Information. It is important to note that Tafel analysis was utilized to enhance image contrast and flake visualization, facilitating the evaluation of the size-activity relationship, rather than for mechanistic investigation or quantitative kinetics analysis. This consideration arises because visualizing nanoplates smaller than 10 μm in lateral size poses challenges, particularly when displaying topographical/activity mapping.

Figure S9–S11, Supporting Information, present SECCM mappings of the HER activity for several Mo₂C flakes of Sample I exhibiting similar behavior as discussed in Figure 2: namely, displaying a homogenous electrochemical activity of the basal plane with consistent and similar current values of individual flakes. These results indicate that the difference between flakes’ morphology has no significant influence on the electrochemical activity for Sample I.

Subsequently, LSV curves were conducted at different scan rates (1, 2, and 4 Vs^{–1}) in a 10 mmol L^{–1} HClO₄ solution (see Figure S8I–K, Supporting Information). As expected, the limiting HER current remained at the same values, and variations in the scan rate did not affect the overpotential for different selected regions of the flake. Using the mass transport limited-current and the wetted footprint of the SECCM meniscus (Figure S5, Supporting Information) the expected current density is around 4.8 A cm^{–2}. Hence, our localized currents (≈800 pA) are indeed consistent with A cm^{–2} magnitude. This reaffirms that our localized currents reside in the A cm^{–2} range, comparable to current densities in macroscopic HER benchmarks,^[5] confirming the capability of SECCM to study HER with high current density due to high mass transport. Conversely, when the electrolyte concentration was increased from 10 to 100 mmol L^{–1} HClO₄, resulting in a decrease in pH, an increase in current was observed (see Figure S8L, Supporting Information). This increment was also noted for the Cu surface, which was attributed to the available H⁺ concentration. These results indicate that no other process than HER occurs on the surface of pristine small Mo₂C nanoplates.

It is noteworthy that commonly $0.5 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$ is employed as electrolyte solution to evaluate the HER activity of Mo_2C nanoplates, with reported high current densities and overpotentials ranging between -200 and -400 mV versus RHE.^[5,8] However, we deliberately chose to work with a diluted HClO_4 solution to decrease the material's activity, accentuating the local activity differences in the basal plane and between flakes of different sizes. The adopted condition also improved the stability of SECCM measurements by mitigating evaporation and ionic strength effects.^[40]

To investigate the effect of size on the electrochemical activity of Mo_2C nanoplates, SECCM measurements were conducted on Sample II (Figure 3). A contrasting trend emerged in SECCM experiments on Sample II compared to Sample I. Figure 3 depicts two distinct-sized flakes in the same SECCM activity mapping: flake 4 on the left side of Figure 3A with $\approx 45 \mu\text{m}$ width and flake 5 (right side of Figure 3A) with $\approx 15 \mu\text{m}$ size. The SECCM map revealed that flake 4 exhibited heterogeneous and lower HER activity than the smaller flake 5.

The basal plane of flake 4, which exhibits non-uniform activity as illustrated in Figure 3A, can be segmented into three distinct regions based on the observed current according to the histogram in Figure 3B. The yellow regions (region 1—red square in Figure 3A), scattered randomly across the basal plane, evidencing the activity heterogeneity, with currents $< 150 \text{ pA}$. Analyzing the behavior of the light and dark blue regions of the basal plane, representing regions 2 and 3 respectively, a transition from a non-uniform to a more uniform current range is observed. Specifically, region 3 demonstrates a more uniform current at $\approx -200 \text{ pA}$ at -0.6 V versus RHE. This is an increase of around -170 pA at -0.6 V versus RHE compared to the yellow areas in region 1. The representative LSV curves of each region are depicted in Figure S12, Supporting Information.

Tafel analysis was employed to enhance comprehension and visualization of the Mo_2C nanoplates activity. The hexagonal structure of the nanoplates is readily discernible for both flakes 4 and 5 (Figure 3C). However, flake 4 exhibited non-uniform Tafel slopes spanning a wide range from 50 to 150 mV dec^{-1} (Figure 3D), indicating the heterogeneity of the local activity. It is important to note that for flake 5 in Figure 3, the activity exhibited higher levels of inhomogeneity compared to flakes of similar lateral size in Sample I (Figure 2 and S8–S11, Supporting Information). This observation was subsequently confirmed by SECCM mapping and corroborated by the Tafel slope mapping in Figure 3A,C, respectively. Specifically, the activity of flake 5 demonstrated a Tafel slope of $\approx 80 \text{ mV dec}^{-1}$ for the basal plane. This finding underscores the significant influence of growth conditions on the Mo_2C surface characteristics.

It is worth noting that the copper substrate in Sample II seems to exhibit a non-uniform and rough surface, as evidenced by two colored regions with distinct HER activity (Figure 3A). However, the scale bar in Figure 3A indicates a similar current range of the copper surface obtained in Figure 2.

The low HER activity of the Mo_2C nanoplates in Sample II, the high subparticle heterogeneity, and the high roughness of the copper surface hampers the clear visualization of Mo_2C nanoplates of Sample II in the SECCM electrochemical mapping. Moreover, as showed in the AFM analysis in Figure S3,

Supporting Information, larger nanoflakes resulted in a reduced thickness, making it difficult to visualize the nanoplates in the topographic SECCM image.

Figure S13, Supporting Information shows AFM topography and height profile of Mo_2C flakes of Sample II, revealing the presence of step-edges, which vary in height between 15 nm and 25 nm . Interestingly, reduced HER activity was discernible at the center of flake 4, indicated by the red arrow in Figure 3A. Tafel plot imaging explicated the well-shaped-low activity region (see Figure 3C), indicating the presence of the step-edge on the center of the flake, as seen in the optical microscopy image in the inset of Figure 3A. When the SECCM tip landed on the step-edge, the majority of the SECCM meniscus possibly contacted either the basal plane of the terrace and bottom layer, as well as the crystalline plane of the step-edge. In other words, SECCM mapping for flake 4 has a higher heterogeneity, probably due to the presence of the step-edges that expose different planes.

Planar HR-TEM images in Figure 3E,F reveal the Mo_2C (021) planes with an interplanar distance of 0.257 nm , which are perpendicular to the (200) planes, as shown in Figure 3F. This observation confirms the presence of the (200) planes on the Mo_2C basal surface. Additionally, cross-sectional TEM images in Figure 3G,H show the (200) planes with an interplanar distance of 0.242 nm , demonstrating that the (001) planes, which are perpendicular to the (200) planes, are exposed laterally in the nanoplate. Figure S14, Supporting Information, reveals that the observed copper oxide particles were removed during the sample transfer to the TEM grid. Consequently, the edge structures observed in TEM represent the clean, intrinsic morphology of the highly crystalline Mo_2C nanoplates.

Therefore, the HER activity at the step-edges reflects the average response of both (200) and (001) planes. The (001) surface exhibits Mo terminations with the C atoms in a sublayer, while the (200) surface features mixed Mo and C terminations. Wang et al. calculated a more negative hydrogen adsorption energy for the (001) planes at low H coverage compared to the (200) planes using density functional theory.^[15] Conversely, at high H coverage, both surfaces showed nearly thermoneutral H adsorption.^[15] Hence, we anticipate that at low H^+ concentrations, the (001) and (200) planes would exhibit distinct HER activity, with the (200) being more active than the (001), thus elucidating the low activity sites at the step-edges observed in the SECCM activity mapping in Figure 3A. Furthermore, since both flake edges and step-edge features expose the (001) crystallographic planes, it is reasonable to conclude that the flake edges and the step edges would exhibit similar intrinsic HER activity, further supporting our interpretation that copper residues do not enhance or dominate the observed catalytic behavior of the flake's edges.

However, the presence of only one step edge in flake 4 depicted in Figure 3A, along with the observation that nanoplates in Sample II without step edges also exhibit a heterogeneous HER response (refer to Figure S15, Supporting Information), suggests that the distinct local electrochemical behavior of flakes synthesized with longer growth times (Sample II) cannot solely be attributed to the presence of step edges.

Figure 4A presents an AFM topographic image, acquired on Sample II, showcasing three different Mo_2C nanoplates, indicated as flakes 6, 7, and 8. Figure 4D displays the height profile extracted from the AFM topography image in Figure 4A for the

Figure 4. A) AFM topography image, B) SECCM HER current, and C) Tafel slope mapping, acquired with a hopping distance of 1 μm , for Mo₂C nanoplates in Sample II. D) Height profile for flakes 6, 7, and 8 extracted from the lines indicated in (A). E) Representative LSV curves of flakes 6, 7, and 7 extracted from the (x, y) coordinates of the current mapping in (B). F) Current histograms for flakes 6, 7, and 8 extracted from (B), only the pixels inside the flakes were considered.

three flakes. Flake 6 in Figure 4D has a lateral size of $\approx 20 \mu\text{m}$ and deeper growth into the copper surface, evident from a significant valley in the AFM height profile. In contrast, flake 7 exhibits a lateral size of $\approx 8 \mu\text{m}$ and edges “buried” in the Cu surface, like the nanoplates in Sample I. Interestingly, flake 8 in Figure 4D reveals the presence of vertically aligned nanoplates, with heights between 400 nm and 600 nm above the copper surface, and a clear elevation of the Cu surface. The topographical SECCM image in Figure S16, Supporting Information was aligned with the AFM analysis, revealing a higher Z extension on the vertical flake.

As anticipated, the 20 μm Mo₂C nanoplates (flake 6) exhibited poor and non-uniform activity, almost indistinguishable from the Cu surface (Figure 4B), with HER currents smaller than 70 pA (Figure 4F). The opposite trend was observed for flake 7, which displayed currents higher than -300 pA at -0.7 V versus RHE (Figure 4F). Conversely, flake 8, the vertical one, showed an intermediate trend with HER currents around -200 pA at -0.7 V versus RHE (Figure 4B,F). The Tafel slope image in Figure 4C shows that the three flakes can be distinguished from the Cu surface due to difference on Tafel slope versus the Cu surface.

As discussed in Figure 3 and confirmed in Figure 4, Sample II exhibited a broad size distribution of Mo₂C nanoflakes, with high heterogeneity in the electrochemical activity toward HER to the big flakes than to the small ones. Moreover, the small flake 7 presented a larger electrochemical activity than the big flake 6. The vertical flake (flake 8) displayed heterogeneous activity, with regions showing a similar overpotential as flake 7 (green curve in Figure 4E), and others with an overpotential of -550 mV versus RHE (light blue curve in Figure 4E). The vertical flake is expected to expose the (001) plane at the surface; thus, a similar activity as the step-edges observed in the horizontal larger flakes is anticipated. Figure S17–S19, Supporting Information, present SECCM HER mapping for vertically aligned Mo₂C flakes,

showing a similar behavior. In these measurements, no Cu oxide nanoparticles are observed in either the AFM image (Figure 4A) or the corresponding SEM images (Figure S17 and S20, Supporting Information), allowing a clean assessment of the intrinsic activity of the exposed crystal planes. These measurements consistently demonstrate that the (001) planes exposed at the flake edges exhibit lower HER activity compared to the (200) basal planes, as revealed by the SECCM current and Tafel slope maps. This reinforces our interpretation that the decreased edge activity is not an artifact of surface contamination, but rather reflects the intrinsic electrocatalytic properties of the Mo₂C crystal facets. However, we encountered challenges in mapping the electrochemical activity of the vertical flakes, such as: 1) Vertical nanoplates had small widths (500 nm—Figure S20, Supporting Information), making it easy to accidentally skip over them with a hopping distance of 500 nm or less, resulting in the loss of important information about their activity, and 2) visualization of vertical nanoplates was complicated due to more heterogeneous flakes of Sample II and copper surface (Figure S19, Supporting Information).

Based on the SECCM measurements at the subparticle level in Sample II, it can be concluded that nanoplates larger than 20 μm in lateral size exhibit a heterogeneous and low HER activity, with currents lower than -70 pA (Figure 3 and 4). The behavior of flakes with sizes ranging between 10 and 20 μm in lateral size differs from larger flakes, showing current values around -200 pA across the entire basal plane, as depicted in the histogram in Figure 3B. This behavior is distinct from that of Sample I, where the shorter growth time led to flakes with sizes smaller than 10 μm and exhibiting currents around -1000 pA at -0.6 V versus RHE (see Figure 2). These findings underscore a clear size-electrochemical activity relationship for Mo₂C nanoplates towards HER.

Bulk electrochemical measurements performed in samples transferred to glassy carbon (GC) surface (Figure S21,

Supporting Information) reveal no clear difference between the HER activity of different Mo₂C samples, which does not reflect the size-dependent heterogeneity that is clearly resolved by the SECCM maps. This result is expected, as the low surface coverage of Mo₂C and the ensemble averaging inherent to bulk measurements obscure the local variations in activity. More important, the LSV curves using standard methods did not achieve mass transport limited current, which is shown in the SECCM LSV curves (Figure 2G–I).

2.2. Comprehensive Structural Characterization of Mo₂C Flakes

The correlative AFM/SECCM mappings demonstrated a distinct correlation between the nanoflake size and the electrochemical activity of Mo₂C. Furthermore, the observed heterogeneity in electrochemical activity for flakes synthesized with longer growth times (Sample II) could not be solely attributed to the presence of step edges. To elucidate the underlying differences in chemical composition between Sample I and Sample II, a comprehensive characterization was conducted, providing deeper insight into their respective physicochemical properties.

XRD analysis was conducted in the Bragg–Brentano geometry on the as-grown Sample I and Sample II. The XRD diffractograms were plotted in logarithmic intensity scales to enhance the visualization of low-intensity peaks, as depicted in Figure 5A,B and S2C, Supporting Information.

Our analysis revealed that the flakes consist of α -Mo₂C (PDF 01-071-0242) with an orthorhombic unit cell, belonging to space group Pbcn, with a (200) surface orientation. This orientation is

evidenced by the prominent peaks near $2\theta = 38.04^\circ$ and 81.37° and $2\theta = 37.99^\circ$ and 81.23° in Sample I and II, respectively. Additionally, flakes oriented along various planes were obtained, such as the (021), (121), (221), (023), and (321) planes, where the (200) plane is oriented perpendicular to the substrate surface. This orientation is facilitated by texturing between the (111) copper substrate and the vertically oriented flakes, enabling the observation of planes perpendicular to the (200) basal surface.

In Sample II, the presence of an unidentified XRD peak at $2\theta = 37^\circ$ was noted and additionally the presence of its second-order diffraction peak at $2\theta = 78.8^\circ$ (Figure 5B and S2, Supporting Information). We hypothesized that the unknown XRD peaks correspond to crystalline (020) and (040) MoO₃ (PDF 01-073-1249) with a monoclinic unit cell belonging to space group P2₁/c. The observation of MoO₃ from XRD indicates that it is likely textured along the (200) basal surface of α -Mo₂C.

Notably, the presence and intensity of MoO₃ exhibited a clear dependence on the synthesis parameters. Sample I, with Mo₂C flakes with lateral sizes smaller than 10 μm lacked the attributed MoO₃ peak, as illustrated in Figure 5A. Conversely, Sample II, with nanoplates lateral sizes ranging from 2 μm to 40 μm , consistently exhibited MoO₃ peaks (Figure S2, Supporting Information). XRD diffractograms on a linear intensity scale in Figure S2, Supporting Information, evidenced the hypothesized MoO₃ peaks are of low intensity and low quantity, making it a challenge to detect additional XRD peaks corresponding to MoO₃. Additionally, the linear scale highlights the sharpness of the Mo₂C (200) peak more clearly, confirming the high crystallinity of the samples. Although the peaks at $2\theta = 37^\circ$ and 78.8°

Figure 5. XRD on as-grown substrates in log intensity scales for flakes in A) Sample I and B) Sample II. Chemical and structural characterization of Mo₂C from C–F) Sample I with 9 μm lateral size and G–J) Sample II with 27 μm lateral width. HAADF-STEM and the corresponding EDS maps showing the distribution of D,H) molybdenum and E,I) carbon throughout the flakes. F,J) SAED acquired along the textured [200] of Mo₂C.

match with monoclinic MoO₂ peaks, we observed significant broadening, which could be related to the presence of molybdenum oxycarbides (MoO_xC_y). To check the presence of a mixture of MoO_xC_y, we simulated powder XRD patterns with x and y being 1:4 and 1:8 ratios between oxygen and carbon.

The simulated diffractograms revealed that substituting oxygen into the Mo₂C lattice increases the (200) and (400) interplanar distances, shifting the diffraction peaks to smaller angles, towards the extra peaks at 37° and 78.8° (Figure S22, Supporting Information). However, a high concentration of oxygen (1:4) results in interplanar distances larger than those associated with the unknown XRD peaks. This indicates that specific, low concentrations and favorable oxygen configurations within the Mo₂C lattice are necessary to reproduce the experimentally observed XRD pattern. Based on both experimental and theoretical XRD analysis, Sample I likely contains a lower oxygen content, insufficient to produce a pronounced (010) MoO₂ peak. In contrast, Sample II exhibits a higher oxygen content, leading to the formation of a well-defined MoO₂ and low intensity peak in the XRD pattern.

Mo₂C flakes were transferred onto a TEM grid utilizing the wet chemical transfer method (as outlined in the Supporting Information). Examination via low-magnification high-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM), as depicted in Figure 5C,G, reveals the hexagonal nanoplate morphology of flakes with 9 μm (Sample I) and 27 μm (Sample II) in lateral length, respectively. Selected area electron diffraction (SAED) from both flakes, shown in Figure 5F,J, unequivocally confirms the high crystallinity of the synthesized α-Mo₂C nanoplates, with the [200] orientation and the (200) plane prominently exposed at the basal surface. Notably, the SAED pattern reveals distinct strong and weak spots, both corresponding to the molybdenum sublattice, with the weak spots indicative of long-range periodic molybdenum lattice distortions induced by ordered carbon vacancies within α-Mo₂C (Figure S23, Supporting Information). Furthermore, TEM analysis showed that the hexagonal nanoplate comprises six grains with facets corresponding to (001) planes, perpendicular to [001], or the zigzag plane of the crystal, as schematically depicted in Figure S23, Supporting Information.^[41,42] Upon close inspection of SAED, we observed a notable difference in the spot pattern. In Sample II, extra spots were observed that could not be indexed to the forbidden reflections in α-Mo₂C (Figure S24, Supporting Information). Furthermore, these extra spots appear to form a hexagonal pattern along with the primary spots. We hypothesize that these extra spots occur due to double diffraction and the presence of stacking faults within the structure.

XPS was conducted directly on the as-grown samples. The survey scan reveals that Sample II contains molybdenum, carbon, and oxygen, as seen in Figure S25A, Supporting Information. The high-resolution Mo 3d spectrum, shown in Figure S25B, Supporting Information, consists primarily of an asymmetric doublet with Mo3d_{5/2} at 228.13 eV, which corresponds to Mo₂C.^[13] A second contribution, with Mo3d_{5/2} at 229.2 eV, is attributed to Mo⁴⁺ presented as MoO₂^[43] and was modeled considering the characteristic satellite features of MoO₂.^[43,44] The high-resolution C1s spectrum, shown in Figure S25C, Supporting Information, was deconvoluted into four components: 1) a peak at 284.7 eV, attributed to sp³ carbon; 2) a peak

at 284.4 eV, which corresponds to sp² hybridized carbon, originating from graphene present in the as-grown sample; 3) a peak at 283.3 eV, which is attributed to carbon in Mo₂C;^[13] and 4) a small peak at 288.3 eV, which corresponds to carbonyl groups. The total carbon/molybdenum ratio (C/Mo) was determined to be 10.8, due to the dominant presence of graphene. Importantly, when considering only the components assigned to Mo₂C (Figure S25, Supporting Information) on each of the high-resolution regions, the C/Mo ratio is 0.57, in close agreement with the stoichiometry of Mo₂C. We pointed out that prior to the SECCM measurements, the graphene formed on the Mo₂C nanoplates was removed via mechanical exfoliation using a Kapton tape, as described in the supporting information (Figure S26, Supporting Information). However, certain flakes with larger lateral size could exhibit irregular surfaces with residual graphene, which may influence the electrochemical performance of these flakes (Figure S27, Supporting Information).

To evaluate the possible composition variation with the lateral size, EDS mappings were acquired both in HAADF-STEM and SEM modes. STEM-EDS mapping shown in Figure 5 and S28–S29, Supporting Information reveals a uniform distribution of molybdenum and carbon in the nanoplates. In the SEM EDS mapping, due to low sensitivity and the effect of Cu substrate, just Mo and C were detected in the nanoplates mapped in the as-grown samples regardless of their sizes (Figure S30 and S31, Supporting Information). STEM-EDS profiles in Figure S29, Supporting Information, reveal a stronger oxygen signal near the edges of the nanoplates in Sample I, whereas in Sample II, the oxygen signal appears uniformly distributed across the basal plane. AFM data indicated a correlation between the lateral size and thickness of the nanoplates (Figure S3, Supporting Information). Specifically, for Sample I, grown with low methane concentrations and short growth times, the nanoplates have lateral sizes below 10 μm and thicknesses ranging from 80 to 150 nm, with oxide formation localized at the edges. Conversely, for Sample II, prepared with higher methane concentrations and longer growth times, the nanoplates exhibit a broader lateral size distribution (5–40 μm) but are thinner, with thicknesses below 50 nm, and oxide formation distributed uniformly across the basal plane.

These findings suggest that native MoO₂ tends to form on the slower-growing surfaces. In short-growth-time samples, the growth predominantly occurs through the basal plane, resulting in smaller nanoplates with oxide localized at the edges. In contrast, longer growth times promote lateral growth, producing larger but thinner flakes with extensive oxide coverage across the basal plane.

Spatially resolved Raman mapping on Sample II was conducted to directly correlate the dimensions and density of native oxide sites (Figure S32, Supporting Information). Characteristic Raman modes of orthorhombic Mo₂C^[45] were observed in Sample II. However, no Raman peaks related to MoO₂ in either the small or large lateral dimension nanoflakes were observed. Significant variations in the Mo₂C peak intensity, position, and width were observed for the large flakes, indicating a heterogeneous crystalline structure. These variations were especially observed in the 143 cm⁻¹ (B_{3g}, A_g) Raman peak likely caused by structural defects or oxygen impurities, which can induce local strain in the crystalline structure. Defects such as stacking faults

Table 1. Comparison of growth conditions, structural characteristics, and HER activity of Mo₂C nanoplates in Sample I and Sample II.

	Sample I	Sample II
Growth condition	CH ₄ -H ₂ concentration of 0.17%, 10 μm thick copper foils, 30 min growth time	CH ₄ -H ₂ concentration of 5.00%, 250 μm thick copper foils, 70 min growth time
Size distribution	5.3 ± 2.4 μm	14.0 ± 12.8 μm
Thickness	>60 nm	<50 nm
XRD Peaks of Mo ₂ C	Peaks at 2θ = 38.04° and 81.37° (α-Mo ₂ C, orthorhombic)	Peaks at 2θ = 37.99° and 81.23° (α-Mo ₂ C, orthorhombic)
Orientation	Basal plane = (200) Edges = (001)	Basal plane = (200) Edges = (001)
XRD peaks of MoO ₂	Not observed	Peaks at 2θ = 37° and 78.8° (MoO ₂ , monoclinic)
Oxidation site	Localized at the edges	Across the basal plane
Step-edge formation	Not observed	Observed with thin copper foils and high methane concentration
Dominant growth mode	Vertical growth through the basal plane	Lateral growth through the edges
HER activity	Uniform activity, enhanced performance	Heterogeneous activity, reduced performance

could account for this shift and the additional spots in the SAED pattern (Figure S24, Supporting Information). The variation observed in the Raman peaks at 215 and 234 cm⁻¹ (Figure S32, Supporting Information) can potentially be explained by the presence of MoO₂ since both Mo₂C and MoO₂ present overlapped peaks at these frequencies, as shown in Figure S33, Supporting Information. We note that Raman mapping revealed the homogeneity of the Mo₂C Raman peak intensity, position, and width of the small lateral size flakes (≈10 μm) which likely reflect the high crystallinity in the nanoplates grown in Sample I which is consistent with the SAED pattern in Figure 5 and S24, Supporting Information.

Based on the findings from XRD and XPS analyses, we propose that the observed variation in the electrochemical activity with large Mo₂C nanoplate in Sample II could be attributed to the 1) presence of step-edges in the flakes with lateral size higher than 15 μm; 2) formation of native molybdenum oxide species during the CVD growth; and 3) presence of few remaining graphene coming from the growth process.

To gain deeper insights into the properties of potentially formed Mo oxide, SECCM measurements were performed on Mo₂C nanoplates where oxidation was induced according to the procedure described in the supporting information. The Raman spectra of the oxidized-Mo₂C sample (Figure S33, Supporting Information) indicated the presence of a MoO₂ layer on the Mo₂C surface. Figure S34 and S35, Supporting Information, depict the SECCM HER mapping of oxidized nanoplates with sizes between 25 and 35 μm, revealing a homogeneous and low activity with HER currents at -0.6 V versus RHE being smaller than -150 pA and a Tafel slopes higher than -100 mV dec⁻¹. Moreover, the edges and some few points on the basal plane still exhibit higher activity, with currents exceeding -300 pA and a LSV profile resembling that of the pristine flake. These results in the induced-oxidized Sample II suggest that the heterogeneous activity observed in pristine flakes of Sample II may be associated with the formation of native MoO₂, in addition to the step-edge formation. Both effects were favored by longer growth times and noticed in large flakes.

As summarized in Table 1, the size-dependent trends in HER activity are clearly observed. In Sample I, the shorter growth time results in smaller and thicker nanoplates with less oxygen content, a smoother surface, and with less residual graphene, and consequently with higher HER activity. Meanwhile, Sample II resulted in bigger and thinner nanoplates with step edges formation, more significant oxygen content, particularly on the basal plane, higher surface roughness, and more residual graphene, leading to a reduced HER performance.

3. Conclusion

The comprehensive analysis of Mo₂C nanoplates using a combination of electrochemical and imaging techniques, including SECCM, SEM, and AFM, revealed insights into their morphology, structure, and electrochemical activity. The correlation between spatially resolved topographical SECCM mapping and morphological analysis indicated that nanoplates with lateral size <10 μm (Sample I) had a well-defined shape with smooth surface and no step-edges (Table 1), while nanoplates grew with high methane concentration and longer times (Sample II) displayed a broad size distribution, irregularities, and defects, likely due to prolonged growth times leading to step-edges and native oxide formation, supported by XRD (Table 1). The nanoplates with lateral size of <10 μm presented at Sample II group exhibited higher electrochemical activity than the large nanoflakes in the same group, clearly evidencing the correlation between size of nanoplate and electrochemical performance for HER. Our findings reveal that the electrochemical activity of α-Mo₂C nanoplates is strongly influenced by the nanoplate lateral size, and consequently by the growth conditions.

The formation of structural defects, step-edges, and MoO_xC_y, favored by longer growth times, high methane/hydrogen concentrations, or thicker copper foils, appears to be key factors influencing the activity of the nanoplates. The investigation also explored the presence of vertical nanoplates in Sample II, revealing distinct growth patterns and crystal orientations, where the (001) facets appear to be less active for HER than the (200) basal plane. Overall, our findings contribute to a deeper understanding

of the structure-activity relationships in α - Mo_2C nanoplates and offer valuable insights for the rational design and optimization of catalysts for hydrogen evolution and other electrochemical applications. Further research in this direction holds great promise for the development of efficient and sustainable energy conversion technologies.

4. Experimental Section

Mo₂C Growth: An overlying 10 μm -thick (Thermo Scientific 99.8% purity) or 25–250 μm -thick copper foil (Thermo Scientific annealed, uncoated 99.8% purity) and underlying 50 μm molybdenum foil (Thermo Scientific 99.95% purity) stack measuring $1 \times 1 \text{ cm}^2$ were placed in an alumina boat (CoorsTM) within a quartz glass tube (27 mm inner diameter, 28 mm outer diameter) in a tube furnace (Thermo Scientific Lindberg Blue M Mini-Mite). The glass tube was purged for 20 min with 650 sccm of ultrahigh purity 15% hydrogen and argon gas mixture. The foil stack was annealed at 1070 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 h in the presence of 450 sccm of flowing argon-hydrogen gas. The furnace temperature was ramped at 4 $^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$ to 1090 $^\circ\text{C}$, and then the final temperature was held for 5 min. Then, 1 sccm of ultrahigh purity 10% methane and argon gas mixture or 3 sccm of methane gas (99.97% purity) flowed for 15–70 min. Mo_2C hexagonal prisms with lateral sizes of 2–50 μm were obtained using Cu foils with thicknesses between 10 and 500 μm , growth times of 30–70 min, and methane-hydrogen concentrations of 0.17–5.00%. We previously evaluated the parameters for the Mo_2C synthesis. Here, we focused on two samples: sample I was prepared in a short time (30 min) low methane-hydrogen (0.17%) on 10 μm thick copper foils, while sample II was synthesized using a long period (70 min) and high methane-hydrogen concentration (5.00%) on 250 μm Cu foils. As depicted in Figure S1, Supporting Information, at the growth temperature, molybdenum atoms diffuse through the liquid copper foil and react with methane on the surface. Following the growth, the foil stack was cooled from 1090 to 800 $^\circ\text{C}$ in 3 min under the protection of flowing argon and hydrogen gas, and finally removed from the hot zone of the furnace and allowed to cool to room temperature. To oxidize α - Mo_2C , the Cu–Mo foil stack was left in the hot zone of the furnace and naturally cooled in 450 sccm of flowing argon gas.

Mo₂C Transfer: Briefly, the transfer involves spin coating PMMA (3000 rpm, 60 s) on the as-grown sample and curing the film on a hot plate at 180 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 90 s. The samples are cut to the desired dimensions and then floated in a 70 $^\circ\text{C}$, 0.2 mol L^{-1} ammonium persulfate solution. After a few hours, the Cu was etched, and the film containing the flakes was scooped and thrice washed in deionized (DI) water. Finally, the film was scooped onto target substrates and dried on a hot plate at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min. The PMMA is removed by placing the substrate into an acetone bath for 6 h, then in isopropyl alcohol, and dried on a hot plate at 60 $^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 min.

Mo₂C Characterization: XRD was performed on as-grown Mo_2C using a Malvern PANalytical Empyrean using Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation as the X-ray source. Surface topography of the pristine and transition metal Mo_2C samples was investigated by tapping mode AFM in air (JPK, NanoWizard 3) using a Si probe with electrically conductive coating of 5 nm Cr and 25 nm Pt on both sides of the cantilever, a resonance frequency of 75 kHz and 3 N m^{-1} force constant. Mo_2C flakes were transferred from Cu–Mo substrates to gold Quantifoil carbon grids using the transfer procedure described previously. The PMMA (A6) was rinsed in acetone for 3 min and isopropyl alcohol for 1 min three times. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed in a FEI Talos F200X operated at 200 kV. SAED was acquired using 820 nm diameter aperture. SAED patterns were analyzed and prepared using DigitalMicrograph and ImageJ software. Simulated SAED patterns were generated using SingleCrystal software distributed by CrystalMaker Software (www.crystallmaker.com). STEM-EDS was acquired using a Super-X EDS detector. EDS analysis and elemental mapping were performed using Thermo Fisher Velox Software. Raman spectra and mapping were acquired using a HORIBA LabRAM HR Evolution spectrometer operated in the backscattering configuration using a 633 nm laser excitation. The measurements were taken with a 100 \times objective and 1800 gr mm^{-1}

grating. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed using a Physical Electronics VersaProbe II instrument equipped with a monochromatic Al $\text{K}\alpha$ X-ray source ($h\nu = 1486.7 \text{ eV}$) and a concentric hemispherical analyzer. The binding energy axis was calibrated using sputter cleaned Cu (Cu 2p_{3/2} = 932.62 eV, Cu 3p_{3/2} = 75.1 eV) and Au foils (Au 4f_{7/2} = 83.96 eV).^[46] Samples were measured directly on the Cu substrate used for their growth. Substrates were fixed to the instrument stage applying double sided adhesive carbon tape. Measurements were made on $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^2$ areas with a pass energy of 27 eV, at a takeoff angle of 45 $^\circ$ with respect to the sample surface plane. This results in a typical sampling depth of 3–6 nm (95% of the signal originated from this depth or shallower). XPS data was fit using CasaXPS v2.3.25PR1.0. No charge correction was applied. Quantification was done using instrumental relative sensitivity factors (RSFs) that account for the X-ray cross section and inelastic mean free path of the electrons.

SECCM Pipet Preparation and Size Measurement: Singular pipets were produced from single-barrel quartz-filamented capillary (ZQF-120-90-10; Science Products) using a CO_2 -laser puller (P-2000; Sutter Instruments). The dimensions of the resulting nanopipette were assessed utilizing SEM with the FEI Quanta 3D ESEM instrument. The determination of equivalent diameters involves a two-step process: first, computing the area of the elliptical opening based on its major and minor axes and subsequently converting this area into the equivalent area of a circle. High-resolution mapping tips with diameters ranging from 130 nm to 170 nm were fabricated using the following parameters in the puller program: HEAT 650, FIL 4, VEL 45, DEL 130, and PUL 120 (Figure S4, Supporting Information).

SECCM Measurements: Electrochemical experiments were conducted using a custom-built SECCM workstation described previously.^[47,48] A single-barrel pipet filled with electrolyte solution was affixed to a pipet holder. The working sample was positioned on top of an x, y, and z-piezo cube (P-611.3S nanocube; PhysikInstrumente) for precise adjustments using an analog piezo amplifier (E-664, PhysikInstrumente). Sample coarse positioning including the x, y, and z-piezo cube involved movement in the x, y, and z-directions until the pipet was $\approx 30 \mu\text{m}$ above the region of interest. This coarse positioning was achieved using three stepper motor-driven micrometer screws (OWIS) controlled by an LStep PCIe (Lang) controller, in conjunction with an optical camera (DMK 21AU04; The Imaging Source) and a cold light source (KL1500 LCD; Schott). The SECCM tip was approached to the sample surface with a predefined feedback current (i_{surf}) with a threshold of -4 pA to detect the SECCM meniscus-surface contact. Electrochemical measurements were carried out within the confined area defined by the droplet cell formed between the SECCM tip and the sample surface. The collection of electrochemical data utilized a standard hopping mode protocol. Briefly, the SECCM tip was sequentially positioned at predefined locations on a grid, and upon each landing, an independent electrochemical measurement (linear sweep voltammetry, LSV) was performed. This process resulted in the acquisition of a spatially resolved voltammetric ($i_{\text{surf}} - E$) image of the sample.

The experimental setup was housed in a Faraday cage equipped with thermal isolation panels (Vaku-Isotherm) and situated on a vibration-damping table (RS 2000, Newport), supported by four S-2000 stabilizers (Newport) to minimize vibrations from the surrounding environment. The potential of the sample surface, employed as working electrode (WE), was precisely controlled versus a quasi-reference-counter electrode (QRCE) inserted into the SECCM tip from the back. The current passing through the QRCE (referred to as i_{surf}) was quantified using a variable gain transimpedance amplifier (DLPCA-200, FEMTO Messtechnik). The process of data acquisition and instrumental control was executed through an FPGA card (PCIe-7852 R) managed by a customized adaptation of the Warwick Electrochemical Scanning Probe Microscopy (WEC-SPM) software. WEC-SPM was originally developed by the University of Warwick and scripted in LabVIEW (National Instruments). The integration of LabVIEW allowed for efficient and tailored control of the SECCM system during electrochemical experiments.

SECCM Mapping of HER Activity: SECCM tips with 130 to 170 nm diameter were employed to acquire local LSV curves of Mo_2C surfaces. To map HER activity, the potential was scanned in the range of 0 to -0.8 V vs Ag/AgCl/3 mol L^{-1} KCl. The experiments were conducted in a (10 mmol L^{-1})

HClO₄ solution under an argon atmosphere, utilizing a scan hopping mode with hopping distances of 500 nm or 1 μm. The reference electrode was Ag/AgCl/3 mol L⁻¹ KCl, and the recorded potential was converted to the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale ($E_{\text{RHE}} = E_{\text{substrate}} + E_{\text{Ag/AgCl/3MKCl}} + 0.059 \text{ pH}$). $E_{\text{Ag/AgCl/3MKCl}}$ is 0.210 V, and the pH of the (10 mmol L⁻¹) HClO₄ solution is 2 not considering the activity coefficients. All SECCM tips used for the HER experiments were consistently fabricated with similar diameters, as confirmed by SEM. The surface area for calculations was determined from SEM images of the pipette aperture, assuming no droplet spreading occurs in the acidic medium. This approach ensures consistency in the experimental setup and allows for accurate comparison of the data obtained across different measurement areas.

Statistical Analysis and Data Processing: Data processing and analysis were made using the electrochemical raw data obtained in TDMS format. The software employed for extracting and processing the data was MATLAB R2024a (Mathworks). MATLAB scripts import TDMS data and organize it into structured tables, separating the desired parameters, such as the electrochemical data as voltage (V), and current (I). SECCM approach data is processed point by point, filtering false approaches (i.e.: no current registration) and extracting x, y, z-location and the desired parameters. For LSV scans, the code applies smoothing, generates voltage-dependent videos, and produces cumulative LSV plots. It visualizes electrochemical data by mapping the current at a fixed potential (e.g., -1 V vs. RHE) across the scanned area, with options to plot line/bullet-style current maps and pixel-specific voltammograms. Most of the SECCM mapping was prepared based on LSV curves at a fixed potential (e.g., Figure 2D, 3A, and 4B). Figure 2G–I and 4E were generated by extracting the current values from individual pixels at specific potentials, without applying any averaging, as each pixel represents a single LSV measurement. This approach facilitates direct visualization and comparison of local electrochemical behavior across different sample regions, including the Cu surface, edge sites, and basal planes. Current histograms (e.g., Figure 3B,D and 4F) were generated by extracting the current values at a fixed potential from each pixel in the SECCM map, where each pixel corresponds to a single LSV measurement. The x-axis represents the current at the selected potential, while the y-axis shows the percentage of pixels exhibiting that current value. This visualization provides a statistical overview of the local electrochemical response and highlights variations across the scanned area. Tafel slopes are calculated by fitting $\log(i)$ or $\log(j)$ versus overpotential from selected pixels, generating point-specific plots and 2D activity maps (e.g., Figure 2E, 3C, and 4C). Separate current and current density plots, along with Tafel slope histograms, were produced. All parameters are customizable, including fitting ranges and regions of interest.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

The manuscript was written through the contributions of all authors. **David E. Sanchez, Alexander J. Sredenschek, and Andres Fest** conducted the Mo₂C growth and XRD, Raman, SEM, and TEM characterization. **Geovane Arruda de Oliveira and Daniel Grasseschi** conducted the SEM, AFM, and SECCM experiments and SECCM data processing in MATLAB. **Moonjoo Kim** helped with the development of data acquisition software for SECCM experiments. **Carla Santana Santos** provided guidance and helped analyze and interpret the SECCM data. **Wolfgang Schuhmann and Mauricio Terrones** supervised the whole work. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript. **Geovane Arruda de Oliveira and David E. Sanchez** contributed equally to this work.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

2D materials, electrocatalysis, hydrogen evolution reaction, scanning electrochemical cell microscopy

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